

SUBSTITUTED BUTYRO LACTONES. PART III. SYNTHESIS OF
 γ -(4-ALKOXY-3-CHLOROPHENYL)-BUTYRO LACTONES

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β -(4-Alkoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids, obtained by succinoylation of 2-chlorophenyl alkyl ethers, have been reduced to furnish γ -(4-alkoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones.

Importance of lactone ring and the alkoxy group (Genge and Trivedi, this *Journal*, 1957, 35, 801, 804) as also of chlorophenyl group (Genge and Kshatriya, *ibid.*, 1958, 35, 521, 525) has been discussed earlier. γ -(4-Alkoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones have been prepared and described in the present communication.

β -(4-Alkoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids, required for preparation of the above lactones, were obtained by succinoylation of 2-chlorophenyl alkyl ethers. Nuguyen-Hoan and Buu Hoi (*Compt. rend.*, 1947, 225, 1228) succinoylated (no details) 2-chloroanisole and 2-chlorophenetole to yield β -(4-methoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)- and β -(4-ethoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids respectively.

Ethyl esters of β -(4-alkoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids were reduced by aluminium isopropoxide, and the resulting hydroxy-acids on lactonisation afforded γ -(4-alkoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Chlorophenyl alkyl ethers were prepared by the action of an appropriate alkyl bromide on 2-chlorophenol in presence of sodium ethoxide.

2-Chlorophenyl-*n*-hexyl ether does not seem to have been described before. It is a colorless liquid, b.p. 261°/760 mm, n_D^{20} 1.537. (Found: Cl, 16.6. $C_{12}H_{17}OCl$ requires Cl, 16.7%).

General Procedure for Succinoylation of 2-Chlorophenyl Alkyl Ethers.—This was carried out as described by Fieser and Hershberg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2314) with the following modifications.

In the succinoylation of 2-chloroanisole and 2-chlorophenetole, nitrobenzene was used as a solvent. The reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 4 hours. In case of higher phenyl alkyl ethers, a mixed solvent was used. The reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 24 hours.

Ethyl β -(4-alkoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionates were reduced by aluminium isopropoxide, as described by Genge and Trivedi (*loc. cit.*) to yield γ -(4-alkoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones. Compounds prepared are shown in Tables I and II.

* In part.

TABLE I

β-(4-n-Alkoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids and derivatives.

No.	Compounds.	Cryst. shape.	M.P. or B p	Formula.	% Chlorine *	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Oxime of <i>β</i> -4-methoxy-P †	Plates from benzene or dil. alcohol	120°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₄ NCl	13.53	13.78
2.	Semicarbazone of "	Needles from dil. EtOH	236°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	11.98 (296.5)	11.85 (299.5)
3.	Ethyl ester of "	Do	90°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄ Cl	12.80	13.12
4.	Methyl ester of "	Do	117°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl	13.69	13.84
5.	Oxime of <i>β</i> -4-ethoxy-P	Plates from benzene or dil. alcohol	130°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄ NCl	13.21	13.66
6.	Semicarbazone of <i>β</i> -4-ethoxy-P	Needles from dil. EtOH	160°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	11.20 (312.1)	11.32 (313.5)
7.	Ethyl ester of <i>β</i> -4-ethoxy-P	Do	70°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	12.10	12.47
8.	Methyl ester of "	Do	100°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₄ Cl	13.23	13.12
9.	<i>β</i> -4-n-Propoxy-P	Needles from alcohol or hot water	180°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄ Cl	13.00 (272.6)	13.12 (270.5)
10.	Oxime of (9)	Plates from benzene	111°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄ NCl	12.63	12.44
11.	Ethyl ester of (9)	Needles from dil. EtOH	66°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ Cl	11.82	11.90
12.	Methyl ester of (9)	Do	80°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	12.39	12.48
13.	<i>β</i> -4-n-Butoxy-P	Do	150°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	12.60 (282.6)	12.48 (284.5)
14.	Oxime of (13)	Plates from benzene or dil. alcohol	118°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ NCl	11.68	11.85
15.	Ethyl ester of (13)	...	190-95°/4mm	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ Cl	11.54	11.36
16.	Methyl ester of (13)	Needles from dil. alcohol	75°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ Cl	11.79	11.90
17.	<i>β</i> -4-n-Amyloxy-P	Do from dil. EtOH or hot water	102°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ Cl	11.73 (296.0)	11.90 (298.5)
18.	Oxime of (17)	Plates from benzene	120°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ NCl	11.48	11.32
19.	Ethyl ester of (17)	...	235-40°/10mm	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₄ Cl	10.33	10.87
20.	<i>β</i> -4-n-Hexyloxy-P	Needles from dil. alcohol or hot water	80°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ Cl	11.50 (311.7)	11.36 (312.5)
21.	Ethyl ester of (20)	...	245-50°/10mm	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₄ Cl	10.31	10.42

* Equivalent weights are shown in parentheses.

† P denotes -3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid.

TABLE II

γ-(4-n-Alkoxy 3-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones and derivatives.

No.	Name of compound.	Cryst. shape.	M.P. or B.P.	Mol. formula.	% Chlorine*.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>γ</i> -(4-Methoxy)-L	Prismatic plates from alcohol	74°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ Cl	15.40 (224.5)	15.67 (226.5)
2.	S-salt of <i>γ</i> -4-methoxy-HB	Plates from water	128°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	8.80	8.67
3.	<i>γ</i> -(4-Ethoxy)-L	Prismatic plates from alcohol	82°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ Cl	14.51 (239.2)	14.76 (240.5)
4.	S-salt of <i>γ</i> -(4-ethoxy)-HB	Plates from water	140-41°	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	8.41	8.38
5.	<i>γ</i> -(4-n-Propoxy)-L		195-200°/3mm	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₃ Cl	13.82 (256.1)	13.95 (254.5)
6.	S-salt of <i>γ</i> -(4-n-propoxy)-HB	Plates from water or alcohol	132°	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	8.03	8.11
7.	<i>γ</i> -(4-n-Butoxy)-L		180-85°/3mm	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl	12.92 (265.3)	13.22 (268.5)
8.	S salt of <i>γ</i> -(4-n-butoxy)-HB	Plates from water or alcohol	128°	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	7.81	7.86
9.	<i>γ</i> -(4-n-Butoxy)-HB	Plates from benzene	80°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ Cl	12.25 (284.3)	12.39 (286.5)
10.	<i>γ</i> -(4-n-Amyloxy)-L		200-205°/6mm	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₃ Cl	12.81 (280.4)	12.57 (282.5)
11.	S-salt of <i>γ</i> -(4-n-amlyoxy)-HB	Plates from water	108°	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	7.53	7.62
12.	<i>γ</i> -(4-n-Hexyloxy)-L		208-12°/6mm	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₃ Cl	11.75	11.98
13.	S-salt of <i>γ</i> -(4-n-hexyloxy)-HB	Plates from water	85°	C ₂₄ H ₃₃ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	(295.5) 7.23	(296.5) 7.40

S stands for S-benzyl isothiuronium.

HB (-3-chlorophenyl)-hydroxybutyric acid.

L (" ")-butyro lactone.

* Equivalent weights are shown in parentheses.

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